

Preparation and Properties of Some *p*-Substituted Benzohydroxamic Acids

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A simple modified procedure for the preparation of *p*-substituted benzohydroxamic acids is described. These are characterised by the infrared and ultraviolet spectra.

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of these hydroxamic acids in water, 0.1M HCl, and 0.1M NaOH have been determined.

The effect of substitution and solvent on the spectra of substituted benzohydroxamic acids is also briefly discussed.

THE various *p*-substituted carboxylic acid derivatives react with hydroxylamine in alkaline solution to form hydroxamic acids(I)

(X = H, CH₃, CH₃O, F, Cl, Br, I, NO₂, NH₂ or CN)
(I)

An examination of the published work^{5,7,9} reveals that the preparation of hydroxamic acid (I) is generally tedious and time consuming. In the present communication a modified procedure is described which saves time and affords analytical grade product in improved yield. The infrared spectra were recorded for the characterization of these hydroxamic acids.

The ultraviolet spectra of the synthesised hydroxamic acids were scanned in water, 0.1M HCl and 0.1M NaOH. An attempt has been made to study the effect of substitution and solvent on the spectra of benzohydroxamic acids.

Experimental

Materials and Apparatus: All the chemicals used were of A.R. Grade of E. Merck.

Ultraviolet absorption spectral measurements were recorded on Beckmann DU and infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 221 spectrophotometer as mulls in nujol.

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General Procedure: A typical preparation of *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid is described below.

Into a 500 ml flask was placed 6.95 g of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in 40 ml of ethyl alcohol and 18.89 g of sodium bicarbonate in 15 ml of water was added. Next, 18.5 g of *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride in 30 ml of ethyl alcohol was added in a period of 30 min. with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0°. The stirring was continued for 15 min. more. The liquid layer was separated and mixed with 20 ml of petroleum ether. Any solid product thus obtained was separated and the alcoholic mixture was distilled under vacuum. The yellowish white solid hydroxamic acid thus obtained was combined with the bulk product and crystallized from alcohol or ethylacetate, m.p. 165°; yield 60%.

The hydroxamic acids are freely soluble in alcohol. In the present procedure this property is used for the preparation of *p*-substituted hydroxamic acid to get the better yield.

All the hydroxamic acids could be prepared by following the above procedure.

Discussion

The physical properties of *p*-substituted benzohydroxamic acids are given in Table 1. The ultraviolet spectra are given in Table 2. All the hydroxamic acids are white crystalline solids except *p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid which is light yellow. These are stable to light, heat and air. They are readily soluble in water except *p*-chloro-, *o*-bromo- and *p*-iodobenzohydroxamic acids which are sparingly soluble but all are readily soluble in dioxane, ethyl acetate, ethyl alcohol and hexanol.

The infrared spectra of ten compounds of the structure I, were examined (Table 1) and this revealed

TABLE I PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF *p*-SUBSTITUTED BENZOHYDROXAMIC ACIDS

Compd. No.	Hydroxamic acid	Mol. Formula	Mol. Wt.	M.p. °C	Yield %	IR Spectra		Analysis %			
						Frequency cm ⁻¹ OH	C=O	Calc. N	Found N	Calc. C	Found C
I	Benzo-	C ₇ H ₇ NO ₂	137.17	128	70	2770	1640	10.21	10.20	61.24	61.15
II	<i>p</i> -methylbenzo-	C ₈ H ₉ NO ₂	151.17	149	65	2790	1645	9.33	9.28	63.49	63.36
III	<i>p</i> -methoxy benzo-	C ₈ H ₉ NO ₃	167.17	158	63	2795	1655	8.38	8.31	57.42	57.44
IV	<i>p</i> -fluorobenzo-	C ₇ H ₆ NO ₂ F	155.13	155	69	2775	1640	9.03	0.04	54.17	54.09
V	<i>p</i> -chlorobenzo-	C ₇ H ₆ NO ₂ Cl	171.62	178	70	2780	1645	8.16	8.06	48.96	48.91
VI	<i>p</i> -bromobenzo-	C ₇ H ₆ NO ₂ Br	216.05	167	67	2775	1650	6.48	6.39	38.89	38.80
VII	<i>p</i> -iodobenzo-	C ₇ H ₆ NO ₂ I	263.04	170	60	2800	1650	5.32	5.29	31.94	31.96
VIII	<i>p</i> -nitrobenzo-	C ₇ H ₅ N ₂ O ₄	182.14	165	60	2810	1660	15.38	15.40	46.13	46.07
IX	<i>p</i> -aminobenzo-	C ₇ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂	152.18	176	65	2770	1640	18.41	18.39	55.20	55.16
X	<i>p</i> -cyanobenzo-	C ₈ H ₆ N ₂ O ₂	162.16	169	65	2790	1645	17.28	17.19	47.02	46.99

TABLE 2. ULTRA VIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA

Compd. No.	UV Spectra									
	Water neutral		0.1M HCl (Acid)		0.1M NaOH (Anion)					
	λ_{max}	10 ⁻³ ϵ	λ_{max}	10 ⁻³ ϵ	λ_{max}	10 ⁻³ ϵ	λ_{max}	10 ⁻³ ϵ	$\lambda_{max(s)}$ / $\lambda_{max(a)}$	
I	225	9.6	226	8.7	214	9.5	266	5.3	1.24	
II	228	19.7	229	10.9	223	9.5	266	5.5	1.19	
III	253	17.8	254	18.3	234	10.7	265	9.5	1.18	
IV	226	7.9	228	8.0	218	8.1	265	5.5	1.21	
V	230	12.8	232	13.0	225	11.9	269	6.1	1.19	
VI	230	12.9	230	13.1	226	11.7	271	6.0	1.27	
VIII	267	11.5	269	12.0	—	—	270 ^a	—	—	
IX	218	8.3	219	8.6	—	—	270 ^a	—	—	
X	236	16.0	236	16.6	231	15.9	293	6.0	1.20	

that all hydroxamic acids exhibited the intramolecular hydrogen bonding (II).

The presence of (OH) stretching vibration is assigned around 2780 cm⁻¹. The lower shift is due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding of the type II, and in conformity with the reported values^{2,3,5}. The (C=O) stretching vibration is assigned around 1950 cm⁻¹.

The ultraviolet absorption spectra of benzohydroxamic acids show a close resemblance with the structurally related compounds viz., amides and substituted amides^{6,8}. In the spectra of benzamide the bands at 225 nm are the benzene bands II and III, respectively. The hydroxamic acids having

also a band around 230 nm confirms the benzenoid absorption.

Fig. 1,

All the hydroxamic acids have bathochromic shifts except the *p*-aminobenzohydroxamic acid, with respect to benzohydroxamic acid. The λ_{max} of all hydroxamic acids is almost identical in water and

Fig. 2.

0.1M HCl (acidic) solution but the spectra in 0.1M NaOH (anion) are different. The anionic spectra of hydroxamic acids have two bands around 225 nm and 265 nm, respectively. The ratio of these two bands is 1.25 ± 0.05 . The same observations was recorded by Vandenbelt¹ for the substituted benzene.

In the *p*-position the inductive (I) effect should be smaller because of increased distance. However, the *p*-position is (from consideration of valency) capable of facilitating tautomerism and hence almost every substituent placed in this position is capable of

exerting a tautomeric (T) effect. If the sign of both I and T is the same, the effect is increased. Thus the methyl group has +I and +T properties and hence the band shifts to longer wavelength by a methyl group. Again in case where a group has a -I and +T properties, the electron withdrawing effects are less in *p*-position, as found in methoxy and halogen substituents. For the methoxy substituents, the +T effect is so much more powerful than the -I effect that they have a greater shift λ_{max} 253 nm.

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